

Effectiveness of box breathing technique on stress and anxiety among menopausal women residing in selected area.

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ABSTRACT

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Effectiveness of box breathing technique on stress and anxiety among menopausal women residing in selected area.

OBJECTIVES:

Primary objective:

To assess the effectiveness of box breathing technique on stress and anxiety among menopausal women residing in a selected area.¶

Secondary objective :

1. To assess the prevalence of stress among menopausal women residing in a selected area.
2. To assess the prevalence of anxiety among menopausal women residing in a selected area.
3. To assess the effectiveness of box breathing technique on stress among menopausal women residing in a selected area.
4. To assess the effectiveness of box breathing technique on anxiety among menopausal women residing in a selected area.
5. To find the association between pre-intervention study findings with selected demographic variables.

INTRODUCTION:

In most cases, women around the world reach menopause between the ages of 45 and 55. After 12 consecutive months without a period, if there is no other evident physiological or pathological explanation, and if there has been no professional intervention, natural menopause is considered to have happened. Menopause-related hormonal changes can have an impact on a woman's physical, emotional, mental, and social well-being. Individual differences in menopausal symptoms both during and after the transition are significant. Some people have few, if any, symptoms. Others may experience more severe symptoms that have an impact on everyday life and quality of life. Individuals may have symptoms for a long time. Menopause can occur for some women earlier than 40 years of age. This 'premature menopause' may result from specific chromosomal defects, autoimmune diseases, or other unidentified causes. So many women develop stress and anxiety related symptoms. To identify box breathing techniques on stress and anxiety, this study conducted. Material and method: The research design that was chosen for this study is Quasi-experimental, non-randomized control group design with non-probability purposive sampling technique, used to collect data. 60 menopausal women's were taken as sample for study. They are divided into experimental and control group.

RESULT:

After intervention on experimental group, level of stress reduced as well as anxiety score were also reduced. In the experimental group, in pretest, 46.7% of the menopausal women had moderate stress and 33.3% of them had severe stress. In control group, in pretest, 6.7% of them had mild stress, 56.7% of the menopausal women had moderate stress and 36.7% of them had severe stress. In pretest, 56.7% of the menopausal women had moderate anxiety and 43.3% of them had severe anxiety. In posttest, 10% of them had mild anxiety, 80% of them had moderate anxiety and 10% of them had severe anxiety. In control group, in pretest, 66.7% of them had moderate anxiety and 33.3% of them had severe anxiety. In posttest., 3.3% of them had mild anxiety, 70% of them had moderate anxiety and 26.7% of them had severe anxiety.

Conclusion: after posttest data analysis it found that box breathing techniques are effective to reduce level of stress and anxiety among menopausal women's. Post-menopausal stress and anxiety is common issue among women's can be minimized by providing this box breathing techniques.

Key words: box breathing techniques, stress, anxiety, menopausal women's,

INTRODUCTION

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Menopause can occur for some women earlier than 40 years of age. This 'premature menopause' may result from specific chromosomal defects, autoimmune diseases, or other unidentified causes. Symptoms associated with menopause include: Changes to the menstrual cycle's regularity and flow can lead to the termination of menstruation; vaginal dryness; pain during sexual activity; and incontinence, sleeplessness or difficulty in getting good sleep; and alterations in mood, depressive symptoms, or anxiety.¹ The menopause transition can cause psychological and somatic disturbances in a woman's life, and over 75% of women may experience some if not all of menopause related symptoms which may include vasomotor symptoms, sleep difficulties, depression and anxiety and urogenital symptoms and sexual dysfunction.

INTRODUCTION ON BOX BREATHING TECHNIQUE:

Stressed-out people all around the world use box breathing, a type of yogic deep breathing. It was developed from the yogic practise of pranayama, or concentrating on the breath, and is also known as sama vritti pranayama. Its common name, "box breathing," indicates the idea that a box has four sides. In order to demonstrate this idea, slowly breathe for a total of four counts: breaths held after four breaths in, four breaths hold, four breaths exhaled, and four more the exhalation. There are other names for this method as well:

4×4 breathing.

4-4-4-4 breathing.

Equal breathing.

Four-square breathing.

Square breathing.⁴

After a stressful situation, box breathing seeks to help you breathe more normally. It's a highly effective and easy relaxation method. It will enhance their focus by promoting mental clarity, physical relaxation, and both.

BACKGROUND OF STUDY:

The three psychological issues that menopausal and post-menopausal women experience the most frequently are anxiety, depression, and stress. Due to social stigmas and an ageing population that is unaware of the issues, females generally ignore these complaints more often than males do. It frequently has an impact on quality of life, due to late diagnosis and treatment is crucial. This review will cover one of the hypothesized causes of these psychological illnesses in post-menopausal women, which is low levels of vitamin D and estrogen. Although the patients may perceive these issues in the beginning, they might have a negative impact on the patients' mental health, need is to increase patients' knowledge in order to promote the mental and physical health of menopausal and postmenopausal women.⁷ Sexual activity reduces throughout menopause, along with a sense of diminished attractiveness and sexual potency.

NEED OF STUDY

Levels of anxiety and depression, mental discomfort, these aspects have a greater impact on the emotional health of life which are all significantly correlated. Women with and without menopause had significantly different quality of life, according to the research. The provision of psychological care to women who are going through menopause periods is strongly implied by this research. It was determined that psychological distress, anxiety, and depression were significant predictors of menopausal women's quality of life.¹¹ Healthy lifestyle behaviour includes self-actualization, health responsibility, exercise, diet, interpersonal relations, and stress management. Improving lifestyle and health promotion is becoming a basic requirement in human cultures. Women can see the health of their family members and play a significant part in educating and transferring a healthy lifestyle to the next generation. Women make up a sizable fraction of the population in all age groups, but their burden of impairment is major and they face unique issues as a result of physiological changes that occur naturally, such as the menopause transition.

PROBLEM STATEMENT :

Effectiveness of box breathing technique on stress and anxiety among menopausal women residing in selected area.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS.

1. Effectiveness:

Effectiveness is the capability of producing a desired result or the ability to produce desired output. When something is deemed effective, it means it has an intended or expected outcome, or produces a deep, vivid impression.¹³ In this study, effectiveness means the degree to which the Box breathing technique is effective on stress and anxiety among menopausal women.

2. Box breathing

Box breathing is a form of yogic deep breathing employed by the United States Navy SEALs and by stressed-out people everywhere. It's also known as sama vritti pranayama, born of the yogic practice of pranayama, or focusing on the breath.

ORGANIZATION OF DATA:

1. In the experimental group, 16.7%% of the menopausal women were aged below 40 years, 30% of them had aged 40-45 years, 20% of them had aged 45-50 years and 33.3% of them had aged 50-55 years. In control group, 6.7%% of the menopausal women were age-below 40 years, 26.7% of them had aged 40-45 years, 40% of them had aged 45-50 years and 26.7% of them were aged 50-55 years.
2. In experimental group, 66.7% of them were married, 26.7% of them were widow and 6.7% of them were separated. In control group, 60% of them were married, 36.7% of them were widows and 3.3% of them were separated.
3. In the experimental group, 33.3% of them had primary education, 26.7% of them had secondary education, 30% of them had under graduate education and 10% of them were post graduates. In control group, 26.7% of them had primary education, 23.3% of them had secondary education, 40% of them had under graduate education and 10% of them were post graduates.
4. In experimental group, 13.3% of them were homemakers , 30% of them were selfemployed, 33.3% of them had government job and 23.3% of them had government job. In control group, 13.3% of them were homemakers, 26.7% of them were

selfemployed, 33.3% of them had government job and 26.7% of them had government jobs.

5. In the experimental group, 33.3% of them had monthly family income below Rs. 25000, 10% of them had monthly income Rs. 26001-40000, 33.3% of them had a monthly income of Rs. 41001-50000 and 23.3% of them had a monthly income above Rs. 50000. In control group, 13.3% of them had a monthly family income below Rs. 25000, 43.3% of them had a monthly income of Rs. 26001-40000, 36.7% of them had a monthly income of Rs. 41000-50000 and 6.7% of them had monthly income above Rs. 51000.
6. In experimental group, 20% of them were primipara, 76.7% of them were multipara and 3.3% of them were nullipara. In control group, 13.3% of them were primipara, 83.3% of them were multipara and 3.3% of them were nullipara.
7. In experimental group, 96.7% of them had natural menopause and 3.3% of them had surgical menopause. In control group, 86.7% of them had natural menopause and 13.3% of them had surgical menopause .

❑ ANALYSIS OF DATA RELATED TO PREVALENCE OF STRESS AND ANXIETY AMONG MENOPAUSAL WOMEN RESIDING IN SELECTED AREA

Table 2: Prevalence of stress among menopausal women residing in selected area

N=30, 30

Stress	Experimental		Control	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Mild (Score 0-13)	0	0.0%	2	6.7%
Moderate (score 14-26)	14	46.7%	17	56.7%
Severe (score 27-40)	16	53.3%	11	36.7%

In the experimental group, in pretest, 46.7% of the menopausal women had moderate stress and 33.3% of them had severe stress. In control group, in pretest, 6.7% of them had mild stress, 56.7% of the menopausal women had moderate stress and 36.7% of them had severe stress.

Fig. 4.1 Prevalence of stress among menopausal women residing in selected area

Table 3: Prevalence of anxiety among menopausal women residing in selected area

N=30, 30

Anxiety	Experimental		Control	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Mild (Score 0-20)	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Moderate (score 21-40)	17	56.7%	20	66.7%
Severe (score 41-60)	13	43.3%	10	33.3%

In the experimental group, in pretest, 56.7% of the menopausal women had moderate anxiety and 43.3% of them had severe anxiety. In control group, in pretest, 66.7% of them had moderate anxiety and 33.3% of them had severe anxiety.

Fig. 4.2 Prevalence of anxiety among menopausal women residing in selected area

ANALYSIS OF DATA RELATED TO THE EFFECTIVENESS OF BOX BREATHING TECHNIQUE ON STRESS AND ANXIETY AMONG MENOPAUSAL WOMEN RESIDING IN SELECTED AREA

Table 4: Effectiveness of box breathing technique on stress among menopausal women residing in selected area N=30, 30

In experimental group, in pretest, 46.7% of the menopausal women had moderate stress and 33.3% of them had severe stress. In post test, 16.7% of them had mild stress, 76.7% of them had moderate stress and 6.7% of them had severe stress. In control group, in pretest, 6.7% of them had mild stress, 56.7% of the menopausal women had moderate stress and 36.7% of them had severe stress. In post test, 13.3% of them had mild stress, 73.3% of the menopausal women had moderate stress and 13.3% of them had severe stress. This indicates that the stress among menopausal women is reduced remarkably after box breathing technique.

Fig. 5.1 Effectiveness of box breathing technique on stress among menopausal women residing in selected area.

Table 6: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of box breathing technique on stress among menopausal women residing in selected area N=30, 30

	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value
Pretest	24.8	4.7	9.5	29	0.0001
Posttest	19.2	3.9			

The Researcher applied a paired t-test for the effectiveness of box breathing technique on stress among menopausal women residing in selected area. Average stress score in pretest was 24.8 which was reduced to 19.2 in post test. T-value for this test was 9.5 with 29 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. It is evident that the box breathing technique is significantly effective in reducing stress among menopausal women residing in selected area.

DISCUSSION

Discussion related demographic variables. In demographic variables majority women's in both control and experimental group are from age group of more than 45 years. In marital status near about 66 percentage of women's are married, 60 percentage are married in control group. 33% women's are primary educated in experimental an group. 33.33% women's are having government job in both groups. Monthly income of 43% women's in control group is having monthly income of 25,000-40000. 76% women in experimental groups are multipara .Among 30 women in experimental groups 29 are having natural menopause. Discussion related to effectiveness of box breathing techniques. In experimental group, in pretest, 46.7% of the menopausal women had moderate stress and 33.3% of them had severe stress. In control group, in pretest, 6.7% of them had mild stress, 56.7% of the menopausal women had moderate stress and 36.7% of them had severe stress. In pretest, 56.7% of the menopausal women had moderate anxiety and 43.3% of them had severe anxiety In posttest, 10% of them had mild anxiety, 80% of them had moderate anxiety and 10% of them had severe anxiety. In control group, in pretest, 66.7% of them had moderate anxiety and 33.3% of them had severe anxiety. In post test, 3.3% of them had mild anxiety, 70% of them had moderate anxiety and 26.7% of them had severe anxiety.

CONCLUSION

Here a quasi-experimental research design was used to conduct research study. 60 samples were taken and divided in two group's i.e. experimental group and control group. Box breathing technique provided to menopausal women among experimental group, after intervention it was found that the box breathing technique was effective to reduce stress and anxiety in menopausal women's.

LIMITATIONS

1. Women willing to participate in study.
2. Women of the age group below 40 to 55 year and has attained menopause.
3. Women who can read write and understands Marathi,Hindi, English

DELIMITATIONS

1. Women having past history of morbidity .
2. Women who have not attended menopause.

Recommendation:

On the basis of the findings of the study following recommendations have been made for the study:

The study can be replicated with larger sample to generalize the findings.

The study can be conducted in different settings to compare the findings

The study can be conducted to assess the stress and anxiety among women.

The study can be conducted on effectiveness of box breathing technique on
menopausal women's

SUMMARY

Now a days due to overpopulation and lifestyle modifications many people develop health related issues. As women's are working hard to achieve their goals so they need to know about how to reduce stress and different anxieties. Study was conducted for 28 day for better improvement of their health status women can continue box breathing technique This chapter also tells that how the research can be used for various purposes and suggests different ways and means that could be adopted in the future to improve the research.

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